

TEACHING FOREIGN LANGUAGES IN PRESCHOOL AND PRIMARY EDUCATION: METHODOLOGY, MODERN APPROACHES

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Abstract: In this article, it will be emphasized about teaching a foreign language to preschool and primary school students, arousing their interest in this subject, and the methods that should be used for this purpose. In this process, it is mentioned how important the role and activity of the teacher and the student are, and what characteristics are required from both sides. Also, the component of the educational process and the importance of linguistics and human psychology and several teaching methods are discussed. includes. Also, the final words explain the topic comprehensively, emphasizing the methods used and their effectiveness.

Key words: Methodology, psychology, teacher activity, language skills, foreign language level, pedagogical skills, primary school, educational process, difficulties in science.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada xorijiy tilni maktabgacha ta'lim muassasasi va boshlang'ich sinf o'quvchilariga o'rgatish, ularda shu fanga nisbatan qiziqish uyg'otish, va shu uchun qo'llanilishi kerak bo'lgan metodlar haqida ham ta'kidlab o'tadi. Bu jarayonda o'qituvchining hamda o'quvchining roli va faolligi qanchalik muhimligi-yu har ikki tarafdin qaysi xususiyatlar talab qilinishi haqida aytib o'tiladi. Shuningdek, o'quv jarayonining tarkibiy qismi va tilshunoslik va inson psixologiyasining ahamiyati va bir qancha o'qitish usullarini o'z ichiga oladi. Hamda yakuniy so'zlar qo'llanilgan metodlar va ularning samarasini ta'kidlagan holda, mavzuni har tomonlama tushuntirib beradi.

Kalit so'zlar: Metodika, psixologiya, o'qituvchi faolligi, til mahorati, chet tili darajasi, pedagogik mahorat, boshlang'ich maktab, ta'lim jarayoni, fandagi qiyinchiliklar.

Абстрактный: В этой статье будет подчеркнuto обучение иностранному языку дошкольников и учащихся начальной школы, пробуждение у них интереса к этому предмету и методы, которые следует использовать для этой цели. В этом процессе упоминается, насколько важны роль и деятельность учителя и ученика, и какие характеристики требуются с обеих сторон. Также обсуждаются составляющая образовательного процесса и важность лингвистики и психологии человека, а также несколько методов обучения. включает. Также заключительные слова всесторонне объясняют тему, подчеркивая используемые методы и их эффективность.

Ключевые слова: Методика, психология, деятельность учителя, языковое мастерство, уровень иностранного языка, педагогическое мастерство, начальная школа, учебный процесс, трудности в науке.

Introduction

It should be recognized that today the demand for knowledge of a foreign language is increasing day by day. Moreover, today it is emphasized that providing schools and pre-school educational institutions with qualified personnel is one of the important conditions for the development of education in our country. It is not an exaggeration to consider that the formation of interest in learning from the primary grade and increasing the teacher's activity

in this process and stabilizing the students' consensus in making the right choice are also important factors.

In fact, in accordance with the decision of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On measures to bring the activities of popularization of learning foreign languages to a qualitatively new level in the Republic of Uzbekistan" dated May 19, 2021 No. PQ-5117, today foreign significant changes and large-scale efforts are being made to popularize languages.

Teaching foreign languages in preschool and primary education is one of the important directions of the educational process. In today's era of globalization, knowledge of foreign languages remains one of the factors that determine the social, cultural and economic success of a person. Therefore, the need to teach foreign languages from an early age is gaining more and more attention. This process must be combined with pedagogical methodology, psychological approach and practice.

The importance of teaching foreign languages from an early age Teaching foreign languages at the pre-school and primary education levels helps to develop a person's ability to receive and master a language. Research shows that the brain activity of young children easily accepts foreign language sounds, words and structures. A young child is flexible and creative in language learning, which speeds up their language acquisition process. At this stage, language learning should be done through games, songs and activities, because children learn most effectively through play.

Methodological principles Communicative approach is used as one of the main methods in teaching foreign languages in preschool education. This approach emphasizes learning the language for practical use. The goal is to give children the ability to speak, listen, read and write in a foreign language. In the communicative method, the learning process is carried out more through oral communication, situation-based exercises and various games. This approach makes children interested in language learning and helps them acquire the language naturally.

Integrative approaches An integrative approach is also important in teaching foreign languages. This approach involves learning a foreign language by combining it with other subjects. For example, subjects such as mathematics, music, science can be taught through a foreign language. This helps children to understand and actively use a foreign language in different contexts. An integrative approach makes the process of language learning more interesting and meaningful, as well as creates an environment of interactive communication between children.

Interactive methods the use of interactive methods in modern education makes the language teaching process more effective. Such methods encourage children to actively participate in learning and put them at the center of the learning process. For example, role-playing games, working in groups, and problem-solving exercises are interesting and active ways of learning a foreign language. Children learn the practical use of language by interacting with each other using such methods.

Psychological approaches Children's age characteristics and the level of psychological development should be taken into account in the process of teaching foreign languages. It is very important for young children to feel emotional and spiritual comfort while learning a language. At this stage, children should not be afraid of difficulties and learn from mistakes in the process of language acquisition. Therefore, the teacher should encourage them, pay attention to their success and have an individual approach to them.

Technological approaches Today, digital technologies play a major role in teaching children languages. Mobile applications, online platforms, multimedia educational materials allow children to learn foreign languages in an interesting and effective way. The use of audiovisual materials, interactive games and video lessons attract children's attention and make their learning process more effective. It also provides an opportunity to strengthen children's language skills with the help of interactive boards and other technological devices.

New trends In recent years, a number of new trends have appeared in the field of foreign language teaching. One of them is the bilingual education system. In this system, children learn two languages at the same time, which helps them to develop language skills more deeply. Bilingual education strengthens not only the foreign language, but also the native language, and also develops multilingual competence in children.

Also, the "CLIL" (Content and Language Integrated Learning) methodology is becoming more and more popular in teaching foreign languages. This method involves teaching different subjects through a foreign language, that is, children learn about other subjects while learning the language. This approach, along with the development of children's language skills, provides them with a broad worldview and multidisciplinary knowledge.

The methodology and approaches of teaching foreign languages in preschool and primary education are constantly improving. Modern teaching methods help children learn the language in an interesting and effective way. Communicative, interactive and integrative methods, technological possibilities and psychological approaches together enrich the process of teaching foreign languages. At the same time, new trends, such as bilingual education and CLIL methodology, help children succeed in the global world.

It is worth mentioning that it is not easy to teach elementary and kindergarten children a language they are not yet familiar with. It is also very important to be able to apply them. It should be taken into account that these methods may change depending on the age and potential of children. Because it is more difficult for children aged 5-6 to understand and memorize information. That is why they prefer mechanical methods in this way. Because of this, giving grammar lessons to students who are just starting out will cause them to lose interest in learning the language. However, the following methods have been evaluated as more effective:

1-Through various games and interesting riddles: In this process, the student will be more interested in this process, feeling like he is in a game. In this case, they will have less mental fatigue.

2- Through songs, poems and age-appropriate cartoons. In this case, it will be easier for them to memorize new words. It will also have a positive effect on their pronunciation.

3- With the help of senses. In this case, the student should try to find fruits and vegetables while holding them with his eyes closed and say their names in the new language he is learning.

4-Different colored handouts, that is, this also increases activity. Writing questions on them increases the morale of the student. In this, more responsibility is required from the teacher than from the student.

In conclusion, primary school students should not accept language teaching as a professional requirement and should work on their mistakes and shortcomings. will be Because every young generation is the foundation of our independent state.

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